

The Court as Stage: Exploring the Performative Dimension of Trial Transcripts

Luca Giovannini
(Potsdam/Padua)

Miriam Schirmer
(TU Munich/Regensburg)

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1. Introduction

Susan Sontag's insight that "[t]he trial is preeminently a theatrical form" (1966: 126) has prompted scholarly exploration into the performative aspect of legal proceedings. This dimension is particularly evident in cases of transitional justice, such as the Nuremberg (1945-46) and Jerusalem (1961) trials for crimes against humanity, as well as the apartheid-related hearings of the South African Truth and Reconciliation Commission (cf. Cole 2007). Previous studies, however, have been mostly non-quantitative and, despite the structural affinity between theatre and trials, have yet to exploit the wealth of computational tools developed for drama analysis.

In this experiment, we created a corpus of trial transcripts following the model set by the *Drama Corpora (DraCor)* project, one of the major infrastructures for the research on theatrical texts (Fischer et al. 2019). A multimodal platform hosting more than 3000 plays in several languages, DraCor offers a range of tools for quantitative analysis, including APIs, SPARQL endpoints, and dedicated Python and R packages, facilitating the immediate investigation of texts onboarded in its ecosystem.

Despite its strengths, there have been few attempts to exploit the DraCor architecture beyond the study of drama. Within computational literary studies, experimental spin-offs such as a poetry-oriented corpus (*PoeCor*) and a corpus of ecocriticism-related texts (*EcoCor*) have been prototyped during hackathons ¹. Regarding cultural analytics, a CLS INFRA-funded fellowship ² has recently enabled the creation of mockup corpora of

¹ See <https://mhpep.github.io/hackathon/>.

² See an overview at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tCV29LPC3hk>.

fanfiction stemming from the GOLEM project (Pianzola et al. 2019). No organic attempt, however, has been made to fully leverage the DraCor infrastructure to tackle another textual typology.

2. Corpus building

Tapping into this potential, we set out to build the *Genocide Trial Transcripts Corpus* (*GenoCor*), a small corpus of trial transcripts. The development of this corpus is facilitated by the structural parallels between these texts and drama. Trial transcripts, like plays, depict individuals ('characters') engaging with each other within a structured framework reminiscent of the act/scene format and include non-diegetic information resembling stage directions.

Our test corpus is assembled from transcripts originating from two genocide trials conducted by the International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda (ICTR) and the International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia (ICTY), respectively addressing events related to the Tutsi genocide (1994) and the Balkan Wars (1992-2001). The texts were scraped from the *Unified Court Records* database³, which features all official documents from the ICTY and the ICT, mostly in .doc and .pdf format. Texts were then converted to .txt format and cleaned up manually before undergoing processing through the *ezdrama* pipeline (Skorinkin 2023). This pipeline utilised syntactic markup previously applied through regular expressions to generate TEI-XML files compatible with DraCor (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Conversion workflow via *ezdrama*.

³ <https://ucr.irmct.org/>.

During the process, several challenges in modelling trial transcripts as drama were addressed. In particular, one had to deal with paratextual materials, which were mostly preserved and encoded in different formats (cast lists, stage directions) and with segmentation issues. The division of the texts into acts and scenes, fundamental for DraCor algorithms, was achieved by encoding individual tribunal sessions (each corresponding to one transcript) as acts and debate phases as scenes⁴. Speakers' names were also consistently normalised and disambiguated, especially when individuals were only identified by their function at that moment (e.g., a generic “witness” within an examination).

As a last step, the corpus was deployed on a local instance of the DraCor infrastructure built with the Docker technology through the procedure outlined by (Boerner et al. 2023). This approach enabled using all DraCor tools for computational analysis on the local corpus without having to commit the transcripts to the platform online.

3. Perspectives

Although the prototype version presented at CUDAN 2023 included only five texts from the Rwanda trials (Figure 2), it nonetheless offered a glimpse into the potential research applications such a dockerised corpus may have. To begin with, *GenoCor* could be queried via the DraCor API, which offers immediate access to a series of metrics useful for quantitative analysis. They range from basic network values (such as 'size', 'averageClustering', 'density', 'averagePathLength', 'maxDegreeIds', 'averageDegree', 'diameter', 'maxDegree', 'numConnectedComponents') to speech distribution metrics (e.g., the number of speakers or various types of word counts). Furthermore, API calls can be used to extract speech snippets according to specific attributes of their speakers stored in the <particDesc> element. On top of the conventional 'gender' attribute, we added here an additional one indicating the role played by the character in the proceedings (e.g., 'judge', 'defense team', 'prosecution team', etc.), thus enabling the extraction of language used by different parties.

Following previous examples from DraCor-based research, we initially considered applying 'distant reading' methodologies to the networks extracted from the trials, e.g., by singling out 'core' and 'bridge' characters within the structures and evaluating whether their network positions align with their roles in the trial, such as that of 'key witness'. Since the structure of trials is not freely arranged by an 'author' but is rather the result of rigid procedures,

⁴ Trial phases include e.g. preliminary matters, examination-in-chief, cross-examination, re-examination, pre-trial/status conferences, judgement, appeal hearing.

however, the resulting network structures were less informative. While it was still possible to identify subclusters aligning with formal or informal trial phases, we do not believe this approach to hold further potential.

Figure 2. Model card and corpus homepage for the GenoCor prototype.

Applying Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques to the analysis of extracted speeches appears instead more promising. Methods such as topic modelling and sentiment analysis might indeed be useful for discerning patterns and nuances within legal discourse. Additionally, researchers might investigate whether significant differences exist between language usage among opposing parties (defence/prosecution) or across genders. On a more theoretical level, another option could involve exploring the theatrical dimension of judicial proceedings, e.g., by doing a comparative analysis of metadata between GenoCor and DraCor corpora, which might reveal how some 'dramatic' structures are mirrored in trial transcripts.

While the GenoCor project is currently on hold, there are several aspects under which the presented prototype could be enhanced in the future. Efforts should be made to transition it from a proof-of-concept product to an open-access database, addressing challenges such as Docker/API limitations and streamlining the onboarding process for new texts. Improving semi-automatic conversion pipelines and reducing the need for manual disambiguation would also be crucial for enhancing corpus building. Moreover, adding more texts from ICTY proceedings would allow for fruitful structural and contextual comparative analyses while refining categories and improving modelling techniques would also contribute to a deeper understanding of the dataset.

4. Authors' contributions

LG and MS jointly planned the project. LG corrected, prepared, and published the corpus. MS provided the texts in digital format and contributed to their cleanup. This preprint was written by LG, who also presented the project at the *Cultural Data Analytics Conference - CUDAN 2023* (Tallinn, 14.12.2023, slides: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10461155>), and revised by MS.

5. References

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